

QUAREP-LiMi: Light Microscopy (LiMi)- Model Revision Process

Version 1.0

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Mission and Scope

The Light Microscopy Model (LiMi-Model) for light microscopy metadata, formerly NBO-Q - (4DN-BINA-OME-QUAREP) is an extension of the Open Microscopy Environment (OME) data model designed to standardize and structure detailed metadata for light microscopy experiments. Its purpose is to capture critical information such as microscope hardware specifications, image acquisition settings, and calibration metrics. This standardization aims to enhance the quality, reproducibility, and interpretability of microscopy data, facilitating data sharing, analysis, and comparison across different experiments and labs. It supports FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles providing tiered specifications that scale with experimental complexity. The model also fosters community involvement and integration with software tools to ease metadata collection and exchange among the various interested parties (IP). Interested parties are for instance specific WGs, microscope hardware component manufacturers, or other members of the QUAREP community.

To secure consistent and sustainable development of the LiMi-Model, the “**Best Practices for the LiMi-Model Revision Process**” guides the production of revised versions as the need arises. This process, outlined in this document, comprises a set of steps involving both QUAREP-LiMi members and community stakeholders to ensure agreement on proposed changes. A revision process can be initiated when an interested party identifies that the current released version (Vn) no longer meets all needs and should be revised. A successful revision process results in a new version (Vn+1) of the LiMi-Model.

Revision Process

The LiMi-Model Revision Process consists of **five major phases** which are depicted in the figure below and are explained in the main text of this document.

Figure 1: The LiMi-Model revision process.

The following abbreviations are used: IG - Interest Group; SG – Stakeholder Group; WG – Working Group (of QUAREP-LiMi); PFC – Proposal For Change; SC – Steering Committee (of QUAREP-LiMi)

Phase 1 Review

At any given time, the currently released version of the LiMi-Model is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/WU-BIMAC/NBOMicroscopyMetadataSpecs>) for use by any and all interested parties.

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If the current version (V_n) does not meet a user's needs, the interested party can form an Interest Group (IG), which initiates Phase 2 of the revision process and is responsible for carrying out all subsequent phases until V_(n+1) is approved.

Phase 2 Preparation

The IG is responsible for assembling a Stakeholder Group (SG). SG members are recruited from the QUAREP-LiMi community and beyond—for example, via a QUAREP-LiMi-wide call, by requesting participation from members of relevant working groups, or by announcing the process on relevant community forums (e.g., image.sc, Confocal Listserver). A suitable SG is expected to include:

1. A sufficient number of well-recognized domain experts from within QUAREP-LiMi and beyond;
2. One or more LiMi-Model experts (e.g., QUAREP-LiMi WG7-Metadata members) who are willing and able to participate in the process and ensure implementation;
3. Representative current adopters of the LiMi-Model (e.g., Micro-Meta App, MethodsJ2, etc.).

It is also advisable for the SG to include liaisons to relevant WGs and, where available, their Content and Model Coordinators (see the "Operation and Output" section of the QUAREP-LiMi Working Group document).

The IG produces a summary document describing the rationale for initiating a revision, along with the composition and credentials of all SG members. This document is sent to the QUAREP-LiMi Steering Committee (SC) for assessment. If the rationale for change and the composition of the SG are both considered sufficient and appropriate, the SC issues formal approval to begin the proposed revision process, initiating Phase 3. As part of this approval, the SC advises the SG on case-specific points of attention relevant to the proposed revisions and on its responsibilities for promoting consensus and avoiding breaking changes, thereby helping to prevent potential problems in Phases 3 and 4.

Multiple revision processes can be initiated and carried out simultaneously. To monitor these processes and update the QUAREP-LiMi community at regular intervals, the SC assembles a Monitoring Group (MG) responsible for shepherding revision processes across all phases and maintaining a roll-call document of approved, ongoing model revisions.

The roll-call document tracks: 1) which parts of the LiMi-Model are currently under revision; 2) the composition of each SG and the role of each member; 3) the phase each ongoing revision process is in; and 4) the composition of the MG.

Phase 3 Revision

The SG operates like a QUAREP-LiMi WG (see the "Operation and Output" section of the QUAREP-LiMi Working Group document) and produces a **provisional Proposal for Change** (PFC) document, which is sent to the SC. All proposed changes to the LiMi-Model must be clearly explained, with the rationale for each change well documented. The PFC must originate by consensus among all SG members, be formatted to promote consistency across different revision processes, and avoid introducing breaking changes elsewhere in the LiMi-Model.

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A SG representative presents the provisional PFC to the SC, which assesses its formal and technical maturity and, if appropriate, approves it. The process then enters Phase 4, and the provisional PFC becomes a **mature PFC**.

Phase 4 Evaluation and Approval

The SC-approved mature PFC is subject to evaluation and approval by the entire QUAREP-LiMi consortium. The SG publicly requests and collects feedback from the consortium. This phase gives the wider QUAREP-LiMi community the opportunity to evaluate the mature PFC, provide feedback, and request changes to reach consensus. The evaluation process shall last a maximum of 30 QUAREP-LiMi working days, but no more than 10 weeks.

The SG ensures that each comment is addressed and that all reasonable feedback is incorporated into the mature PFC to produce a consensus PFC. Where a comment is not accepted, the SG must provide a clear rebuttal and a clear plan for addressing the issue. Acceptable SG responses are:

1. Reversion to the original version.
2. Postponement of addressing the comment until the next version.
3. A detailed explanation of why the comment cannot be addressed.

As part of this process, the SG attempts to resolve potential conflicts directly with the person providing the feedback. In cases of difficulty, the SG and the SC may refer the matter to the Ombuds Board.

At the end of the evaluation process, the SG is responsible for producing the **consensus PFC**. A SG representative presents the consensus PFC to the SC for final approval. This is an essential final step in the revision process and must be carried out in a manner that respects the considerable work carried out by the SG; any rejection must be appropriately justified by the SC.

If the consensus PFC is approved by the SC, the revision process enters its final phase.

Phase 5 Implementation and Release

The SG is responsible for merging and implementing the SC-approved consensus PFC into the LiMi-Model. The result is a new revised release version of the LiMi-Model V(n+1).

Abbreviations

CMC	Content and Model Coordinator
EC	Executive Council
ERB	Editorial Review Board
IG	Interest Group
OB	Ombuds Board

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PFC	Proposal for change
SC	Steering Committee
SG	Stakeholder Group
WG	Working group

Release Notes Version 1.0

This is the initial document released on Zenodo describing the revision process for the Light Microscopy Model (LiMi-Model) for light microscopy metadata. Future versions of this document will summarize in this section the changes relative to the previous version. Major changes will increase the major number (here “1”); minor changes and corrections will increase the minor version number (here “0”).